

aromatic rice cultivars. The cytoplasmic base has been diversified to protect future rice hybrids from outbreaks of disease or insect pests. Breeding indica / tropical japonica hybrids has begun with the development of CMS lines in the background of tropical japonica. ■

Developing Pusa 3A, a Basmati CMS line

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Basmati rice occupies a significant place in India's rice economy on account of its high export potential. With the release of Pusa Basmati 1, the first high-yielding semidwarf Basmati variety meeting quality standards, India leaped ahead in Basmati rice production. Further improvement in Basmati yield may be possible with the adoption of hybrid rice technology.

Various Basmati rice lines were testcrossed with IR58025A. Pusa Basmati 1 showed complete sterility and proved to be a perfect maintainer of wild abortive (WA) cyto sterility. The pollen sterility in the F_1 hybrid was 100%. The F_1 was backcrossed to Pusa Basmati 1 and a BC_1 population of about 600 plants was raised. All the plants showed 100% pollen sterility. Segregation was observed for various plant characters. Twenty BC_1 plants that were closer to Pusa Basmati 1 for various characters were backcrossed to Pusa Basmati 1. About 30 seedlings in each of the 20 BC_2 progenies showed 100% pollen sterility. Cooking quality of the 20 pollen donors was analyzed. The best five donors showing good cooking quality were selected on the basis of their similarity to Pusa Basmati 1 for various agronomic characters such as plant height, panicle length, spikelet morphology, and days to 50% flowering. These plants were again backcrossed to the selected five pollen donors, thus maintaining the identity

of the pollen donors for the respective population. The BC_3 plants raised from the above crosses were screened for pollen sterility; all the plants were 100% sterile. Three plants were selected from each BC_3 progeny row and these were again backcrossed to their respective pollen parent from Pusa Basmati 1. Progenies from pollen plants No. 1 and 3 (Pusa Basmati 1-1 and Pusa Basmati 1-3) had all the morphological characters of Pusa Basmati 1. They were further backcrossed to their respective pollen plants—Pusa Basmati 1-1 and Pusa Basmati 1-3, both with excellent cooking quality traits. The CMS line derived from Pusa Basmati 1-3 has been named Pusa 3A. This line shows stable sterility under different environmental conditions at New Delhi and Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, during the two different rice seasons. This line is now being used extensively for test-crossing with both Basmati and non-Basmati male parents. A few promising combinations with Basmati restorers have been identified. It was also found that heterosis with non-Basmati restorers was far greater than with Basmati restorers for various characters, including yield. ■

Screening rice genotypes for thermosensitive genic male sterility reaction

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Two-line rice hybrids were found to be more heterotic than three-line hybrids. Constraints of the three-line system can also be avoided in the two-line system. Any rice variety can be used as a pollen parent in the two-line system irrespective of the presence of a restorer gene. The two-line system also offers the advantage of easy seed production. For photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterility (PGMS) vs thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS), the TGMS system is more useful for the weather

conditions that prevail in southern India. We therefore screened some diverse genotypes to identify potential lines. Staggered sowings and plantings were done during the 1995-96 wet and dry seasons. We carried out pollen studies on these lines and also recorded spikelet fertility. Data on pollen sterility were correlated with minimum, maximum, and daily mean temperatures during the critical period of sensitivity of the lines, that is, 10 d from the third day after panicle initiation.

During the 1995 wet season, one TGMS line—IR68949-5-31-34—exhibited complete pollen and spikelet sterility for a period of 51 consecutive d. The mean daily temperatures during this 51-d period were between 27.1 and 28.4 °C. The same line transformed to partial fertility when the average temperatures reached 26 °C and below.

During the 1996 dry season, a second TGMS line, IR68945-33-4-14-40, was found to be completely sterile for a period of 15 d. The mean daily temperature regimes at the critical period of sensitivity ranged from 23.5 to 26.5 °C. Later, this line transformed to partial or complete fertility. The two TGMS lines identified in this study may be used to develop new two-line rice hybrids for enhancing heterosis and thus production and productivity of the rice crop. ■

Identifying parental lines in hybrid rice by RAPD fingerprinting

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The commercial production of hybrid rice hinges on three-line breeding, male sterile, maintainer, and restorer lines. Developing and producing new parental lines are essential for the sustainability of hybrid rice. Characterizing these lines based on morphological and phenological characters consumes time, lacks sufficient resolving power, and is influenced by